

Comparative Performance Analysis of Machine Learning and Regression Models for Predicting the Angle of Repose of *Sericea lespedeza* Seeds

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ABSTRACT

Flow properties play an important role in handling and processing food products especially during flow from hoppers, mixing, transportation, compression, and packaging. In recent years, machine learning (ML) has gained popularity in modeling complex and nonlinear processes. The objective of this study was to develop ML models to predict the angle of repose of *sericea lespedeza* seeds based on cultivar and seeds' moisture content, length, width, thickness, and weight. Prediction models were developed using support vector regressor (SVR), random forest regressor (RFR), decision tree (DT), backpropagation neural nets (BPNN), and K-nearest neighbor (KNN) learning algorithms and their performance was compared with regression models. Data for modeling were obtained from an experimental study at the Food Engineering Laboratory, Fort Valley State University, where seed properties were inputs, and the angle of repose was the output. Each model was validated using a ten-times 10-fold cross-validation with five-times 5-fold nested cross validation technique to prevent underfitting and overfitting. Various statistical indices, including Pearson correlations (R) between actual and predicted outputs, were evaluated to select the best models. Prediction plots for angle of repose values indicated that the ML models RFR, KNN, and DT demonstrated robust accuracy ($R > 0.98$), outperforming SVR, BPNN, and regression models ($R = 0.77, 0.74, \text{ and } 0.79$, respectively). Additionally, ML models showed better generalization and interpolation of unseen patterns within the training domain. The analysis highlights the potential of AI to enhance predictions in nonlinear decision contexts without compromising performance in linear decision contexts.

Keywords: Ensemble learning (RFR); Tree-based algorithm (DT); Instance-based method (KNN); Artificial neural networks (ANN); Seed flow properties; Moisture content.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sericea lespedeza (SL, *Lespedeza cuneata* (Dum.-Cours.)) is a leguminous plant of growing agricultural significance due to its diverse applications. Its seeds are rich in protein, tannins, and fiber, making them a valuable renewable

feedstock and a potential source of anthelmintic bioproducts (Muir *et al.*, 2017). These seeds can be used in various applications, including animal feed, biofuel production, and soil conservation (Mosjidis, 1996). However, efficient handling and processing are crucial to fully realize their industrial potential.

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A critical aspect of seed handling is understanding and predicting the flow properties of seeds. This is primarily evaluated by the angle of repose, a key indicator of how granular materials - such as seeds - flow. The angle of repose is the steepest angle relative to the horizontal plane at which a pile of material remains stable without slumping (Al-Hashemi and Al-Amoudi, 2018; Zaalouk and Zabady, 2009).

Seeds with a lower angle of repose form flatter piles and flow more easily due to reduced internal friction and resistance between individual seeds. Conversely, seeds with a higher angle of repose form steeper piles and tend to flow less freely, indicating greater internal friction and interlocking (Teferra, 2019; Madrid *et al.*, 2022). This can lead to issues such as clumping, bridging, or arching in storage and handling systems like hoppers and chutes. Therefore, understanding the angle of repose is essential for designing appropriate equipment for storage, transport, and processing, ensuring smooth flow and industrial efficiency (Teferra, 2019). Poor flowability, for example, can hinder conveying, metering, and blending operations, ultimately increasing operational costs (Al-Hashemi and Al-Amoudi, 2018; Madrid *et al.*, 2022).

Numerous studies have evaluated seed flowability by considering factors such as cultivar type, moisture content, length, width, and thickness as independent variables affecting the angle of repose (Rosentrater and Bucklin, 2022; Mahapatra *et al.*, 2019; Al-Hashemi and Al-Amoudi, 2018; Teferra, 2019). Different cultivars of the same crop can vary in physical characteristics, such as size, shape, and surface texture, which affect flow behavior and packing density. Studies have shown that such variations influence the mechanical and physical properties of the seeds, affecting how they interact and pile (Owolarafe *et al.*, 2007; Izli, 2015). This makes the cultivar type a critical variable in understanding the characteristics of the angle of repose

Moisture content is known to alter surface friction and cohesion between particles. As moisture content increases, adhesion between seeds generally rises due to capillary and viscous forces, resulting in a higher angle of repose (Bhabani *et al.*, 2022; Suleiman *et al.*, 2015). This is particularly important for grains stored in environments with fluctuating humidity. Additionally, the length, width, and thickness of seeds determine their shape and sphericity, influencing how the grains align and behave when piling. Seeds with irregular shapes or lower sphericity tend to interlock more and slide less easily, resulting in higher angles of repose (Aviara *et al.*, 1999; Coşkuner and Karababa, 2007). In contrast, smoother and more spherical particles typically flow better and have lower angles of repose.

Machine learning (ML) models - including support vector regression (SVR), random forest regression (RFR), decision trees (DT), backpropagation neural networks (BPNN), and K-nearest neighbors (KNN) - offer a promising approach to predicting seed flow behavior. These models can learn complex relationships between seed characteristics (e.g., moisture content, size and shape) and flowability, enabling accurate predictions of the angle of repose (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2017). Such predictive capability is invaluable for optimizing storage and handling practices to maintain ideal seed flow conditions. Machine learning models also play a crucial role in the design of efficient processing equipment. By understanding seed flow properties, engineers can design components such as hoppers and conveyors that handle and process seeds more effectively, reducing operational issues and energy consumption (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, ML models enable real-time monitoring and predicting flow behavior, allowing for automated adjustments to processing parameters. This improves efficiency, consistency, and overall performance in seed processing operations (Madrid *et al.*, 2022).

This study utilizes advanced machine learning models to predict the angle of repose of *Sericea lespedeza* seeds based on their physical properties, with a focus on the AU Grazer™ and Serala cultivars. The objective of this study is to enhance understanding of seed flow behavior to support decision-making in agriculture and industry. By leveraging ML, operational efficiency, innovation, and sustainability in the use of *Sericea lespedeza* seeds can be promoted.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental Procedures and Dataset Preparation

Experimental data for developing machine learning models were collected from studies conducted at the Food Engineering Laboratory at Fort Valley State University. Mahapatra *et al.* (2019) outlined the methods used to measure the physical and thermal properties of seeds, as well as the angle of repose for two *Sericea lespedeza* cultivars - AU Grazer™ and Serala. Parameters included seed length, width, thickness, weight, and angle of repose at five moisture levels; 8.57, 12.24, 17.07, 24.33, and 26.53% (wet basis).

To analyze seed dimensions and shapes analysis at each moisture level, 100 seeds were randomly selected from each cultivar. Dimensions, length, width, and thickness were measured with an electronic digital caliper, while individual seed weights were determined using a precision digital balance. Table 1 shows the range of observed values for all parameters, and Fig. 1 illustrates a typical SL seed's dimensions.

The angle of repose was measured using the funnel method, where seeds flowed through a funnel onto a flat surface, forming a conical shape. The resulting pile's height and base diameter were recorded to calculate the angle of repose using the eq. (1) by Altuntaş and Yildiz (2007):

$$\text{Angle of repose, } \theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r) \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, h is the pile's height, mm and r is the base radius, mm.

The two *Sericea lespedeza* (SL) cultivars—AU Grazer™ and Serala were chosen for their distinct morphological and agronomic characteristics, making them ideal for assessing variations in flow behavior, especially the angle of repose. Machine learning models were developed to predict the angle of repose (output) based on input features, including cultivar type, moisture content, dimensions and weight. The algorithms included support vector regression (SVR), random forest regression (RFR), decision trees (DT), backpropagation neural networks (BPNN), and K -nearest neighbors (KNN), with comparisons to traditional regression models.

2.2. Machine Learning Software

Data analyzed was done using JMP Pro 17 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA), an analytics platform combining machine learning and statistical modeling. Cultivar type was encoded using binary coding (AU Grazer™ as 0 and Serala as 1) to treat it as a categorical variable without bias. Models were trained on raw data without feature engineering.

2.3. Selection of Datasets for Training and Validation of Models

Due to a relatively small dataset of 120 records (12 per moisture level), this study used a ten-times ten-fold outer cross-validation with a nested five-times five-fold inner cross-validation technique to reduce potential biases in machine learning performance estimates (Vabalas *et al.*, 2019; Varma and Simon, 2006). This approach avoided under- and overfitting during model development, ensuring reliable performance evaluation. This k -fold nested validation technique consists of two levels of cross-validation: the outer level estimates the model's generalization error. In contrast, the inner level determines optimal hyper parameters for each model.

Table 1. The range of seed property for AU Grazer™ and Serala cultivars of Sericea lespedeza across five moisture content levels.

Cultivar type	Moisture Content (M_c), % w.b.	Length (L), mm	Width (W), mm	Thickness (T), mm	Weight (M), mg	Angle of Repose (θ), °
AU Grazer	8.57	1.28–2.31	0.99–1.50	0.63–0.99	1.90–3.30	17.22–19.06
	12.24	1.60–2.34	1.00–1.52	0.43–1.00	0.80–3.40	18.26–19.48
	17.07	1.68–2.45	1.10–1.51	0.58–1.05	1.10–2.60	18.62–20.18
	24.33	1.65–2.50	1.05–1.56	0.58–1.04	0.90–2.50	20.25–21.78
	26.53	1.78–2.74	1.12–1.77	0.54–1.01	1.10–3.50	26.75–28.03
Serala	8.57	1.62–2.36	1.12–1.51	0.48–1.00	0.90–3.00	19.43–21.21
	12.24	1.62–2.41	1.09–1.49	0.52–0.99	1.00–2.70	19.17–20.16
	17.07	1.64–2.54	1.20–1.66	0.62–1.11	1.10–3.10	19.51–20.31
	24.33	1.74–2.55	1.15–1.68	0.58–0.88	1.00–2.68	19.73–21.30
	26.53	1.79–2.63	1.26–1.69	0.58–0.98	1.00–2.90	29.21–31.04

Fig. 1. Illustration of geometry of a typical SL seed.

For the outer k -fold cross-validation (10 folds), the records were randomly divided into ten equal folds (sets). The model was trained on $k-1$ folds (training set = 9 sets) and tested on the remaining

fold (testing = 1 set). This process was repeated ten times, with a different fold used for testing each time. Within each outer loop iteration, the training set ($k-1$ folds) underwent a further five-

fold inner nested cross-validation. This involved dividing the training set into five sets, using four folds for training and one - fold for validation. This process was repeated five times, with a different fold serving as the testing set each time.

The best-performing configuration from the inner loop was selected and used to train the final model on the combined outer training set, excluding the validation fold. Performance of the final model was evaluated on the held-out validation fold from the outer loop. At the outer level, the performance metrics from all K validation folds, such as accuracy, precision, and recall, were averaged to provide a more reliable and generalizable estimate of the model's performance on unseen data.

2.3. Machine Learning Algorithms Compared

2.3.1 Support vector regressor algorithm

Although primarily known for classification, support vector machines (SVMs) can also handle regression tasks through a variant called support vector regressor (SVR) (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004). SVR seeks the optimal hyperplane in a high-dimensional space that best fits the training data, allowing for a specific level of deviation from the perfect fit without penalties (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004). This approach offers advantages such as robustness to outliers and effective pattern detection in datasets (Drucker *et al.*, 1996). A key feature of SVR is its use of kernel functions to handle non-linear relationships by mapping data into higher dimensions (Müller *et al.*, 2001). Selecting the appropriate kernel and its parameters, along with other hyper parameters like C (regularization) and epsilon, is essential for optimizing SVR performance and achieving a balanced model that avoids underfitting and overfitting (Schölkopf *et al.*, 1998; Chapelle and Vapnik, 1999). Despite its exceptional resilience, particularly in high-dimensional spaces, SVR requires careful hyper parameter tuning and may face computational challenges with large datasets (Hsu *et al.*, 2008).

2.3.2 Random Forest regressor algorithm

Random Forests (RFs) are powerful ensemble learning algorithms known for constructing robust and accurate prediction models by leveraging the "bagging" technique, which combines predictions from multiple individual decision trees (Cutler *et al.*, 2011). Each tree is trained on a random subset of the data and uses different features at each split point. This "forest" of trees collectively votes, resulting in a single model for making accurate predictions, enhancing diversity, and reducing overfitting (Breiman, 2001; Rodriguez-Galiano *et al.*, 2015). While Random Forest Regressors (RFRs) provide strong predictive performance across diverse datasets and can handle complex data, they come with significant computational and memory demands, especially for large datasets. Additionally, RFRs involve hyper parameter tuning, such as the number of trees and 'mtry,' for optimal performance. The "mtry" parameter controls the number of features considered at each split during decision tree creation within a random forest. A smaller "mtry" is preferred for high-dimensional data to prevent overfitting, while a larger value might be suitable for low-dimensional data to capture complex relationships (Abbasi *et al.*, 2021). Random Forest Regressors provide strong predictive performance and can handle complex data, making them valuable tools across diverse fields. However, their execution requires careful management of computational resources and meticulous hyper parameter tuning to mitigate overfitting and achieve optimal performance (Ben Ishak, 2016).

2.3.3. Decision tree learning algorithm

Decision trees are a non-parametric supervised learning method for classification and regression tasks. The objective is to create a model that predicts the target variable's value by learning simple decision rules from the data features. Functioning as a series of interconnected "if-then" statements, a DT forms a segmented prediction

model (Quinlan, 1986). The recursive division of a dataset is based on the features that best separate the data into distinct groups or classes, resembling a hierarchical tree structure. The root node signifies the entire dataset, branches represent splits based on specific features, and leaves represent the final predicted classes or values (Quinlan, 1986).

Decision trees are highly interpretable, with paths from the root to the leaves explicitly capturing the decision-making process. This transparency aids in understanding the model's inner workings and identifying features with the most decisive influence (Ben-Gal *et al.*, 2014). Decision tree learning algorithms can handle numerical and categorical data while providing easy visualization. However, they may suffer from overfitting, instability, and high computational costs. Techniques such as pruning and hyper parameter tuning address these issues (Song and Lu, 2014). Additionally, decision tree algorithms can be sensitive to feature scaling, as different scales may introduce a bias towards features with larger values. However, feature scaling is frequently applied to mitigate this sensitivity (Song and Lu, 2014).

2.3.4. Multilayer perceptron with backpropagation algorithm

A multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network with a feedforward architecture was chosen because of its ability to learn complex relationships in nonlinear data (White, 1992). The MLPs provide universal approximation capabilities and compact representations, making them suitable for the present study (Isabona *et al.*, 2022). The network consists of an input layer that receives data, hidden layers that perform computations using transfer functions, and an output layer that makes predictions (Russell and Norvig, 2022). Neurons within each layer utilize non-linear activation functions (e.g., sigmoid, tanh, ReLU), crucial for transforming input into output. Backpropagation (BPNN) with gradient descent optimization to enhance prediction

accuracy and data fit was employed. Backpropagation iteratively adjusts weights based on the difference between predicted and actual outputs, propagating errors backward through the network (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2015). This optimization process can be supported by techniques like grid search, random search, and Bayesian optimization (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2015).

2.3.5. K-nearest neighbor learning algorithms

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a supervised machine-learning algorithm recognized for its simplicity and versatility. It can be applied to classification and regression tasks, operating on the principle that data points with similar features will likely yield similar outcomes. Without explicit model building, KNN retains all data points during training (Dehariya *et al.*, 2010). It identifies the *K* nearest neighbors of a new data point for prediction. It predicts its class label (classification) through majority voting or its value (regression) by averaging the values of its neighbors (Arya *et al.*, 1998). The user-defined parameter *k* determines the number of neighbors considered. The algorithm employs different distance metrics tailored to the specific problem to gauge the similarity between data points, including Euclidean, Manhattan, or Minkowski distance (Zhang and Zhou, 2005).

The KNN algorithm has several advantages, such as being simple, flexible, and adaptable to different data types. It does not require assumptions about the underlying data distribution or training phase. Additionally, it can handle noisy and missing data by using weighted voting or imputation methods (James *et al.*, 2013). However, the KNN algorithm has some drawbacks, including being computationally expensive and sensitive to the choice of *k*, the distance metric, and irrelevant features. Furthermore, KNN's performance can deteriorate in high-dimensional data scenarios (James *et al.*, 2013).

2.4. Selection of an Optimal Model Configuration

The objective of ML models is to perform well on data not used during training. Therefore, each model’s performance was assessed using a validation dataset. Since the validation dataset consists of new data records unseen by the model, its performance on this set is a more reliable indicator of generalization than performance on the training set (Gosukonda *et al.*, 2015).

Network configurations were determined empirically, and their performances were evaluated across the training, testing, and validation datasets using statistical metrics defined in eq.(2–6). To evaluate the ML models' performance in this study, several statistical indices were used, including the Pearson correlation coefficient (R), standard deviation, bias factor, accuracy factor, root mean square residual (RMSR), mean absolute relative residual (MARR, %), and mean relative percentage residual (MRPR, %).

However, model performance was primarily evaluated using the R value, with the highest R values indicating the best-performing models. The mathematical expressions of the indices used are provided below.

$$RMSR = \sqrt{\sum (O - P)^2 / N} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{Bias factor} = A.\log \sum \log (P/O)/N \quad \dots (3)$$

$$MARR = 1/N \times \sum |O - P| \times 100/O \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{Accuracy factor} = A.\log \sum |\log (P/O)| / N \quad \dots (5)$$

$$MRPR = 1/N \times \sum (O - P) \times 100/O \quad \dots (6)$$

Where, N is the number of data records; O is the observed value; P is the predicted value and A.log is antilog.

2.5. Statistical Regression Models

Regression models were developed using Microsoft Excel (version 2024) with a dataset of 120 records. The objective was to evaluate the

quantitative effects of factors such as sericea lespedeza variety, moisture content, length, width, thickness, and weight on predicting the angle of repose. Excel was chosen for its accessibility and ease of use, facilitating efficient model construction, analysis, and visualization.

This combination of tools enabled a streamlined and transparent modeling process that supported reproducibility and facilitated clear comparisons between the performance of regression and machine learning models. Final regression equations were derived, and additional plots were created to visually compare the predictive performance of both machine learning and regression models.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Regression Equation

After comparing linear, nonlinear, and polynomial models, Eq. 7 was chosen for its superior fit to the experimental data, as indicated by a lower standard deviation and a higher regression coefficient. Polynomial contrasts further confirmed a highly significant cubic trend in the angle of repose ($p < 0.01$).

$$\theta = -3.592 + 0.486 C + 0.301 M_c + 11.792 L + 1.816 W - 4.993 T + 0.953 M \dots (7)$$

Where, θ is angle of repose,°; C is cultivar type; M_c is moisture content, % w.b.; L is length, cm; W is width, cm and T is thickness, cm.

3.2. Prediction Performance of Machine Learning and Regression Models

Table 2 summarizes the performance of six different learning algorithms in predicting the angle of repose for Sericea lespedeza seeds. The models evaluated include SVR, RFR, DT, BPNN, KNN, and a traditional Statistical Regression model. The performance of the models was assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient ($R \pm SD$ (Standard Deviation)), Mean Relative Percentage Residual (MRPR), Bias Factor, Mean

Absolute Relative Residual (MARR), Accuracy Factor, and Root Mean Square Residual (RMSR). These metrics provide a comprehensive understanding of each model's predictive accuracy, bias, consistency, and generalization capability.

Table 2. Pearson's correlations ($R \pm SD$) between predicted and observed values and statistical indices of machine learning and regression models.

Learning algorithms	$R \pm SD$	MRPR	Bias Factor	MARR	Accuracy	RMSR
Support Vector Regressor	0.77 ± 2.88	-0.88	1.00	8.51	1.09	1.33
Random Forest Regressor	0.99 ± 3.73	-0.01	0.99	2.29	1.02	0.55
Decision Tree	0.98 ± 3.74	0.12	0.99	2.88	1.03	0.74
Backpropagation	0.74 ± 4.76	4.16	0.94	15.62	1.18	3.81
K-Nearest Neighbor	0.99 ± 3.73	-0.13	1.00	2.06	1.02	0.55
Statistical Regression	0.79 ± 3.36	-0.88	1.00	8.51	1.09	1.33

SD: Standard Deviation; MRPR: Mean Relative Percentage Residual; RMSR: Mean Absolute Relative Residues

3.2.1. Pearson correlation coefficient ($R \pm SD$)

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between predicted and actual values. A higher R indicates a better model fit. In this study RFR (0.99 ± 3.73) and KNN (0.99 ± 3.73) achieved the highest R values, suggesting near-perfect linear correlation and low prediction variability. DT (0.98 ± 3.74) also performed strongly, slightly below RFR and KNN. On the other hand, SVR (0.77 ± 2.88) and Statistical Regression (0.79 ± 3.36) showed moderate correlation, while BPNN (0.74 ± 4.76) had the lowest R value, reflecting weaker predictive strength and higher variance. These results suggest that ensemble (RFR) and instance-based (KNN) models capture the underlying data patterns more effectively than this dataset's neural networks or linear models.

3.2.2. Mean relative percentage residual (MRPR, %)

The MRPR quantifies whether a model tends to overpredict (positive values) or underpredict

(negative values). It is beneficial because it expresses residuals as a percentage, making it easier to compare performance across different models and datasets (Sakthivel *et al.*, 2019). The BPNN (4.16%) exhibited a pronounced overprediction bias. In contrast, DT (0.12%) showed a negligible overprediction tendency. The RFR (-0.01%), KNN (-0.13%), SVR (-0.88%), and Statistical Regression (-0.88%) all displayed minor underprediction tendencies. The near-zero MRPR values for RFR and KNN indicate well-balanced predictions, while BPNN tends to overestimate the angle of repose.

3.2.3. Bias factor

A bias factor 1 indicates no bias; values above 1 reflect overestimation, while those below 1 indicate underestimation (Ross, 1996). The SVR, KNN, and Statistical Regression all had bias factors 1.00, indicating effectively unbiased predictions. The RFR and DT (0.99) were very close to ideal, while BPNN (0.94) revealed a notable overestimation trend. These findings align with the MRPR results, confirming that BPNN

systematically overpredicts, while the other models are largely unbiased.

3.2.4. Mean absolute relative residual (MARR, %)

Graphical analysis of model predictions showed that the SVR algorithm underestimated at higher values, while the BPNN underestimated at lower ranges and overestimated in the midrange (Figs. 3A–E). In contrast, RFR, KNN, and DT models showed strong agreement between predicted and observed values, outperforming both BPNN and SVR.

Machine learning algorithms offer several advantages over traditional statistical regression models, particularly their ability to detect nonlinear relationships between input and output variables and capture interactions among dependent variables without explicit modeling efforts (Sargent, 2001). Neural networks, for example, consist of numerous processing elements or neurons organized in layers, each with weighted inputs, transfer functions, and a single

output (Agatonovic-Kustrin *et al.*, 2000). The hidden layers between the input and output layers significantly enhance the computational power of multilayer perceptron (MLP) architectures using backpropagation. However, in this study, the BPNN algorithm demonstrated the lowest predictive performance among the models evaluated. This underperformance may be attributed to the dominance of a single influential feature—moisture content—affecting the output values. The BPNNs typically perform better when multiple influential input variables are present.

Furthermore, sensitivity analysis identified moisture content as the primary contributor to the angle of repose, potentially affecting the predictive performance of specific machine learning algorithms, including BPNN. A significant advantage of ML modeling over statistical techniques is that ML algorithms do not require data to satisfy standard distribution assumptions, such as normality and homogeneity of variance (Sargent, 2001). However, data normalization may enhance ML performance.

Fig. 2. Trends in the angle of repose of sericea lespedeza seeds predicted by SVR, RFR, DT, BPNN, KNN, and regression models.

Fig. 3. Predicted vs. actual values of the angle of repose for *Sericea lespedeza* seeds, illustrating model performance for five machine learning algorithms:

(A) Support Vector Regression (SVR),

(B) Random Forest Regression (RFR),

(C) Decision Tree (DT),

(D) Backpropagation Neural Network (BPNN), and

(E) k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

The results of this study demonstrate clear evidence that the machine learning (ML) models developed strong correlations between seed physical properties and the flow behavior (angle of repose) of *Sericea lespedeza* seeds. The machine learning models used in the study, such as RFR, KNN, and DT, exhibited superior predictive accuracy, with Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.99 ± 0.03 , 0.99 ± 0.03 , and 0.98 ± 0.04 , respectively. The elevated correlation values signify a robust association between the input factors (seed qualities such as moisture content, length, width, thickness, and weight) and the output variable (angle of repose).

Moreover, the data presented in Table 2 indicate that the machine learning models (RFR, KNN, and DT) exhibited markedly lower Mean Absolute Relative Residual (MARR) values (2.29%, 2.06%, and 2.88%, respectively) in comparison to other models, such as SVR, BPNN, and regression models. This suggests that the ML models more precisely represented the differences in the angle of repose as affected by seed properties. The MRPR values of these ML models were either near zero or somewhat negative, signifying a balanced prediction tendency without substantial over- or under-prediction.

The research highlights that machine learning models demonstrated superior generalization and interpolation, effectively capturing the intricate, nonlinear correlations between seed characteristics and the angle of repose. The visual representation of prediction plots (Fig. 3) further corroborated this, demonstrating that the predictions from ML models closely matched the actual observations across varying moisture levels. Conversely, regression models and specific machine learning models, such as BPNN, exhibited considerable discrepancies from the actual data, inadequately capturing the seed flow dynamics. The data collectively affirms that the ML models successfully identified and delineated the correlation between seed features and their flow behavior, yielding more dependable predictions than traditional regression models.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Machine learning models offer significant advantages over traditional experimental methods for predicting the flow properties of *Sericea lespedeza* seeds. These models can reduce measurement time and cost, enhance prediction accuracy, and facilitate the exploration of a broader range of scenarios and parameters. Furthermore, ML approaches can reveal complex relationships between seed characteristics and flow behavior, supporting the optimization of seed processing and planting systems. This study presents a comparative analysis of machine learning and regression models for predicting the angle of repose of *Sericea lespedeza* seeds. Model development was conducted without data pre-processing, using raw experimental inputs. Despite the limitations of a relatively small dataset, a *K*-fold nested cross-validation strategy was used to minimize the risk of underfitting or overfitting, ensuring more robust performance evaluation. Among the models tested, RFR, KNN, and DT significantly outperformed SVR, BPNN, and traditional regression methods in cross-validation accuracy. These results highlight the capacity of ML models to generalize from limited and variable biological data, making them effective tools for predicting the angle of repose.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors know of no conflicts of interest associated with this publication, and there has been no significant financial support from third parties other than funding from the USDA for this work that could have influenced the outcomes.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Ramana M. Gosukonda: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Supervision. **Aftab Siddique:** Investigation, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing. **Ajit Kumar Mahapatra:** Conceptualization, Data Collection, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Supervision, Project administration.

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